

THE HISTORY OF THE COUNCIL OF THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN OF THE FEDERATION OF PROFESSIONAL ASSOCIATIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

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ABSTRACT

Studying the history of professional unions helps to understand the role of the human factor in the development of society better. During the totalitarian era, professional union organizations, which were national institutions built into the system of governance, became more and more widespread. That is why today the study and generalization of the activity of professional unions during the independence of the republic of Uzbekistan arouses great political and scientific interest. Studying it allows professional associations to objectively assess the conditions of activity, identify the causes of defects, learn from the past and develop it in modern conditions. As a result, the main goal of the article is to study the history of the Council of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, a professional union of the Republic of Uzbekistan during the period of independence

At the current stage of Uzbekistan's development, the work of fundamentally changing the way of thinking of the society and the forms of country management is being completed. Today, the development of public organizations, which has become one of the areas of building a free democratic society, is one of the priority tasks of the country's construction. These include, in particular, the professional associations of Uzbekistan, which have a rich history and have a significant role in any political system of the society, especially in the conditions of our independence.

Before discussing the future of the professional union movement in the future, we should have knowledge of the historical origin of professional unions during their emergence and formation, as well as the trends of historical development in that period. The study of the history of professional unions allows to analyze the development, dynamics and possibilities of public organizations, especially professional unions, in the conditions of the existing forms of the country's administration [6].

The Council of the Professional Union of Uzbekistan was part of the Central Council of Professional Unions of the United-professional Union until 1991, when Uzbekistan gained independence. After the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 25 professional unions were established in the republic, they adopted their branches and were registered with the Ministry of Justice. In 1991, the professional association of Uzbekistan was established by these 25 professional associations [3].

Since then, the recreating works have been carried out with the participation of a number of regional professional unions. During these periods, there were some problems in the work of the professional associations, but they did not eliminate the necessity. After all, in the last few years, professional associations have become a necessary part of our society.

Today, 12 professional associations serve within the Karakalpakstan Council. There, about 240,000 professional associations are working to ensure labor-related, socio-economic rights and interests, and create decent working conditions in enterprises, courts and organizations. Among them, the construction, structure and directions of work of the professional unions of Uzbekistan, including the professional unions of Karakalpakstan has changed [5].

From the first years of our country's independence, attention has been paid to the development of non-governmental, non-commercial organizations in new political, public and economic conditions. In the second year of our independence, the adoption of the Law "On Professional Unions, Their Rights and Guarantees of Activity" established the legal status of professional unions as the largest public institution in our country.

Today, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Professional Unions" was adopted in 2019 based on the requirements of the time and taking into account that this law has fulfilled its function from a historical point of view and is obsolete in the current system of labor relations [2].

Based on this new law, the workers of the professional unions will be provided with social protection, support for the union, implementation of public control in the consideration of labor disputes, protection of the interests of workers, participation in solving the issues of securing their socio-economic rights, regulatory and legal documents. The rights to participate in the development of projects have been expanded.

In recent years, professional unions have organized their activities in line with the deepening of democratic reforms in our country and the reforms implemented on the development of civil society, increasing the civic dedication of their members, expanding and deepening the scope of democratic renewal in professional unions, has been carrying out a lot of work on strengthening the order of establishment, implementation and investment in the bodies of the professional association.

Today, the main focus is on the social protection of each worker in the labor unions, the structure of primary organizations in all enterprises and organizations, regardless of the type of ownership, and the recruitment of workers operating in small business entities. In the reporting period, a distribution plan was drawn up from the Department of Statistics of the Republic of Karakalpakstan on the newly established enterprises from the social insurance department of the Union Council, and in the reporting period 6354 the enterprise attracted 43,410 employees to the membership of the professional union, public contracts were established in these economic entities and social protection of employees was ensured.

19 billion workers, pensioners, former workers, children of workers, women, low-income

families and citizens included in public contracts accepted by courts, enterprises and organizations on the basis of annual national guidelines were distributed 66 mln. 602 thousand soums (of which 4 billion 109 million 602 thousand soums from professional unions, 14 billion 957 million soums from employers).

In our country, 60% of the country's budget expenditures are directed to the socio-cultural sphere: education, medicine, culture, and social protection of the poor. Reliance on national capabilities, mutual aid and community support are one of the strengths of our nation. Basically, the neighborhood institute takes its place in this regard.

Today in our country, the tactics of the human factor have risen to a high level of value. President Sh. Mirziyoyev's idea on "People want to be happy today, not tomorrow" and turning it into the dominant direction of today's policy was also included in this essence [1]. The implementation of this principle, the humanitarian policy implemented in our country, gives new meaning to people's lives. Adoption of the program to build low-cost houses based on updated model projects in rural areas, mainly taking into account people's wishes and desires, changed people's thoughts about living and working. According to the program, in 2017, model and high-rise buildings with a total area of more than 3.5 million square meters appeared in cities and villages.

In 2017-2020, a program for the construction of 945 high-rise residential buildings in cities was adopted. For low-income families, affordable apartment buildings with about 50,000 apartments will be built in the city of Tashkent, the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional centers and large cities. Basically, in 2017, only those multi-apartment houses with a total area of more than 800,000 square meters were built and handed over to residents. Of course, the fact that 420,000 square meters of housing in the city of Tashkent itself commissioned shows the extent of the work that has been started. However, it would be wrong to say that ensuring the well-being of the population is only related to the issue of housing. The reason is that dozens of problems have accumulated in the same social sphere for many years, and as a result, it has prevented our people from living a normal life.

Let's take one problem that has plagued people for years - the problem of roads. It was also taken under the control of our country. Currently, in our country, on the basis of the development program of road and road-transport infrastructures of regional and local importance, 1,7 thousand km of public highways are being built and reconstructed, 10,4 thousand km of rural highways. Capital and repair works are being carried out on road surfaces in cities, towns, district centers, city-type castles, and rural settlements.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the life of our people in the years of independence in Karakalpakstan, as evidenced by the examples we have seen is a big history which our ancestors have preserved centuries-old history and culture without losing it. Studying and promoting them today is the duty of every person, and thus it is of great importance in educating the future youth. The services rendered by the devotees of our country for our people are shown and used as an example in our daily life. On the one hand, their work is used as a life experience, and on the other hand, it is considered to educate the future generation by teaching these experiences. The reforms carried out in our country are of great importance in improving the socio-economic life of our people, for the overall development of our country, for the well-being of our people's life, for providing them with social protection and necessary opportunities. Therefore, we will achieve the prosperity of the people only behind the work of

the people who came out from among the people. They were historical ancestors who cared for their residents in every situation and served for the development of political, socio-economic and cultural life.

References:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Erkin va farovon demokratik O'zbekiston davlatini birgalikda barpo etamiz. -Toshkent, "Ozbekiston" NMIU, 2017. – 29 b.
2. 2019-jılı Ózbekstan Respublikası «Kásiplik awqamları haqqında»ǵı Nızamı
3. Ayupov M. Ózbekstan kásiplik awqamları kommunistik qurılısı ushın gúresde.- T., 1959. Óziniń. Ózbekstan kásiplik awqamları háreketi tariyxınıń birpara sorawları.- T., 1969 jil.
4. Ózbekstan kásiplik awqamları tariyxınan ocherklar.- T., 1967 jil.
5. Qudiyarova T. Qaraqalpaqstandaǵı kásiplik awqam tariyxı (1917-1941 jıllar) Avtoreferat – N 2005 J
6. Камалов С. Қарақалпақлардын халық болып қәлиплесиўи хәм оның мәмлекетшилигиниң тарийхынан. – Нөкис. 2001

